

The use of virtual reality scenarios in science: Results of a design-based research experiment

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Short abstract

We are witnessing a decline in student interest in science and technology, which is often attributed to the abstraction of science concepts, the scope of the content and teacher-centred approaches. The use of VR simulations appeared promising in the COVID-19 period, when access to laboratories was scarce. For VR simulations, the pedagogical scenarios seem very important. This design-based research aims to explore the pedagogical and didactic potential of computer-based VR scenarios for postsecondary science courses. A mixed methodology relying on individual questionnaires and group interviews was deployed on seven sites with 39 teachers and 5,759 students, grounded in Pintrich's expectancy-value model of motivation and engagement, the TAM3 technology acceptance model, the theory of interest, and Mahlke's (2008) model of user experience. After using the simulations, both teachers and students reported advantages, but these varied quite a bit depending on who was responding. While teachers focus on the pedagogical advantages, such as diversifying teaching methods, students focus first on the affective aspects of the experience (fun, perceived enjoyment, etc.) and also on some advantages for learning (e.g., visualization). Multilevel regression models show that the scenario scores, associated with quality and complexity, are an important and significant variable at the teacher level.

Extended abstract

Goals

This design-based research aims to explore the pedagogical and didactic potential of computer-based virtual reality scenarios for postsecondary science courses.

Problem and context

Despite the importance of science in our society, we are witnessing a decline in student interest in science and technology (Potvin & Hasni, 2014). The abstraction of the concepts, the scope of the content and teacher-centred approaches are possible explanatory factors. Furthermore, biology and other disciplines cover a very wide range of content (Bristol, 2014), encouraging teachers to lecture.

Teaching methods based on active learning have been shown to be a promising solution (Freeman, 2014), especially when combined with technology. VR simulations, which allow for errors and offer access to inaccessible realities or rare, specialized equipment, were used extensively during the COVID-19 pandemic period, when access to science laboratories was greatly reduced. Computer-based simulations improve the learning and understanding of both theoretical concepts and laboratory techniques while arousing interest (Martinez-Jimenez et al., 2003). The instructions and support embedded in the pedagogical scenario built around the simulations seem to be the most important factor in the effectiveness of VR simulations (Merchant et al., 2014), which led us to focus on the scenarios rather than the simulations themselves.

Methodology and conceptual framework

This DBR project brought together 39 teachers and 5,759 students from one university and six colleges, over three iterations that took place between January 2021 and June 2022. It relied on the use of Labster simulations for biology, chemistry and physics courses, and on pedagogical scenarios that teachers built with tools developed and adapted from the Jeffries model (2012) by the researcher and the instructional developer team.

A mixed methodology relying on individual questionnaires and group interviews was deployed with teachers (7 interviews) and students (21 interviews). The group interviews are based on user experience (Mahlke, 2008), as well as their overall perceptions of the simulations. In all, 65 individual interviews were conducted with teachers after they tested the simulations in class.

After completing a simulation, the students answered a questionnaire pertaining to different aspects of motivation, based on Pintrich's (2003) expectation-value model, Poellhuber's (2020) adaptation of certain scales, the students' behavioural, emotional or cognitive engagement (Fredrics et al., 2004) and interest (Hidi & Reddinger, 2006), and some scales from the TAM3 model (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008), in order to predict their intention to adopt. Learning was measured through a learning perception scale (Poellhuber et al., 2020). The students' answers to open-ended questions on their first impressions were processed using Iramuteq lexical analysis software.

The pedagogical scenarios were analysed and rated based on 11 criteria from an analysis of the teachers' individual interviews. Multilevel regressions were performed to predict the students' behavioural engagement.

Interview and open question results

After exploring the simulations, the teachers immediately identified educational potential benefits, realism and fun. They viewed the simulations as complete and able to improve and diversify their teaching, apply theory, allow for visualization and contextualize learning. The students immediately reported the fun and engaging aspect of the simulations, as well as features that help learning: contextualization, laboratory preparation, visualization and self-pacing.

In their answers to the survey question on their first impressions, the terms most frequently used were: interesting, game, like, understand, realistic, easy, fun, learn. A graphical co-occurrence analysis shows four main groups of words; a) learning, course, discipline; b) interesting, like, laboratory; 3) fun, game, video; d) understand, easy.

Survey results

The questionnaire scales generated high scores, with learning perception and situational interest being the highest. Variables associated with affect scored higher than those associated with task value. The results decreased slightly but significantly for almost all scales between iteration 1 in winter 2021 and iterations 2 and 3.

Table 1. Scales mean comparison between iterations

Dimension	#	Iteration			p		
		1	2	3	1-2	1-3	2-3
Learning perception (Poellhuber et al.)	7	5.45	5.29	5.35	0.015	0.257	0.809
Triggered situational interest (Hidi & Renniger)	7	4.98	4.88	4.73	0.486	<0.001	0.080
Maintained situational interest (Hidi & Renniger)	7	5.55	5.37	5.37	0.004	0.002	1.000
Emotional engagement (Skinner)	7	5.26	5.04	4.94	<0.001	<0.001	1.000
Comparative affective value (Poellhuber et al.)	5	3.68	3.74	3.63	0.397	0.850	0.041
Perceived enjoyment (TAM3)	7	5.44	5.23	5.10	0.008	<0.001	0.286
Behavioural engagement (Skinner)	7	4.61	4.67	4.47	0.602	0.018	<0.001
Usefulness and relevance (TAM 3)	7	5.07	4.88	4.88	0.015	0.009	1.000
Comparative usefulness value (Poellhuber et al.)	5	3.40	3.51	3.51	0.025	0.018	1.000

In the multilevel regression analysis (table 2), for the students, gender, self-efficacy, personal interest and ease of use are significantly related to behavioural engagement.

For the teachers, the academic level and the scenario score are significant variables.

Table 2. Multilevel regression analysis to predict behavioural engagement

Level 1	Model 1			Model 5		
	β	t	p	β	t	p
Constant	4.75	81.137	<0.001	4.980	23.301	<0.001
Gender				0.037	0.978	0.328
Disabled				0.008	0.158	0.875
Computer anxiety (TAM 3)				0.468	3.372	<0.001
Triggered situational interest				0.132	5.393	<0.001
Maintained situational interest				0.119	3.454	<0.001
Emotional engagement				0.055	2.377	0.018
Comparative affective value						
Perceived enjoyment (TAM 3)				0.148	0.517	0.605
Usefulness and relevance				0.131	3.290	0.001
Comparative usefulness value				0.029	0.836	0.403
Level 2 (teacher)						
Gender						
Grade level				-0.220	-1.501	0.139
Scenario score				0.086	3.807	<0.001
σ_e^2		0.97829			0.71698	
σ_μ^2		0.17893			0.07975	
ρ		0.155			0.100	
χ^2		582.3			220.8	
DF		65			58	
p		<0.001			<0.001	
Deviance		7399			4995	
Estimated parameters		3			14	
Continuous variables		Centred				
Approximation		Full maximum likelihood				
R_1^2		0.312				
R_2^2		0.494				

The analysis of the student interviews and answers to the open questions highlights the most appreciated aspects of the educational scenarios. The students appreciated the short presentations of the simulations' key elements (briefings) and the teachers' support during the simulations and feedback on the most important aspect and/or a directed discussion in the debriefing phase. The highlights from the teacher interviews converged on certain aspects.

Regarding the difficulties encountered, the students mainly mentioned problems related to language and occasional technical problems. Many would have liked to have more freedom in the simulations.

Theoretical and educational significance of these results

This research shows that it is possible to deploy computer-based VR on a large scale. Simulations seems to engage students affectively, a result corroborated by qualitative and quantitative results. The co-occurrence analysis is very consistent with the TAM3 model, showing the importance not only of ease of use and task value (learning or understanding), but also of perceived enjoyment, an affective variable. The students appreciated the simulations more in the semester when they had little or no access to the laboratory, in line with the theoretical usefulness of VR. The teachers' experience of VR is conditioned by a teaching-potential lens, which may point to a conceptually different user experience.

This research also confirms the importance of supporting the students throughout the educational scenario. This is the only teacher variable that considerably influences behavioural engagement. Finally, this DBR provides concrete avenues for improving pedagogical scenarios, as well as tools to support teachers in developing their scenarios.

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